

Ce³⁺ DOPED YTTRIA NANOPOWDERS FOR TRANSPARENT YTTRIA CERAMICS PREPARED BY PRECIPITATION METHOD

Nibu Putenpurayil Govindan, Monika Micháľková, Dušan Galusek

*Centre for functional and surface functionalized glass, Alexander Dubcek University of
Trencin, Studentska 2, 91150 Trencin, Slovak Republic*

ABSTRACT

In optics, transparency is the physical property of materials allowing light pass through it without being scattered. Transparent polycrystalline ceramic (TPC) materials have attracted a significant attention as candidates for various applications, including laser gain media in solid state lasers, electro-optical devices and scintillators. Yttria (Y₂O₃) is widely known as a promising optical material owing to its broad range transparency, high melting temperature (2430 °C), outstanding refractoriness and excellent chemical stability. Therefore, polycrystalline transparent yttria ceramics have been exploited as perfect candidate to replace single crystals in various applications, including transparent windows, missile domes, bulb envelopes and laser host. Our results report on preparation of Ce³⁺ doped Y₂O₃ nanopowders by precipitation method using ammonium hydroxide as precipitation agent. The influence of precipitation agent and concentration of reactants, morphology, particle size and degree of agglomeration was evaluated. Partly agglomerated powders with the primary size of Y₂O₃ nanoparticles ~200 nm with cubic crystal structure were prepared. The optimum concentration of ammonia precipitation agent was found to be 0.5 M. Ultrasonic deagglomeration of the powder was most efficient if the pH value was adjusted to 11 through addition of NH₄OH water. Stabilisation of the suspension was reached by the addition of Dolapix CE64 or Darvan CN. The green compact prepared by vacuum-pressure filtration method has the relative density about 43 %.

Keywords: Y₂O₃, Transparent ceramics, Zeta potential

INTRODUCTION

Transparent ceramics are attractive optical materials that offer many advantages over single crystals, including greater shape control, higher homogeneity of the dopant, and faster and lower cost fabrication methods. The field of transparent ceramics starts in 1960's with the development of translucent Al₂O₃ for lighting applications [1–3], and slowly expanded into other areas including transparent arm [4], lasers [5,6], and scintillators [7]. To date, various transparent ceramics with high purity and high density have been produced, including simple oxides such as MgO, Y₂O₃, and ZnO, composite or complex oxides such as ZrO₂–Y₂O₃, Y₃Al₅O₁₂, spinel (MgAl₂O₄), and AlN, for applications in solid-state lasers, electro-optical

devices, X-ray scintillators, and thermally conductive components [8–10]. Among transparent ceramic materials yttria ceramics has been developed for applications in e.g. solid state lasers. Y_2O_3 transparent ceramics are also very efficient NIR-visible up-converters, and can be used as materials for X-ray scintillator applications [11]. Our results report on preparation of $Y_{1.99}Ce_{0.01}O_3$ nanopowders by precipitation method using ammonium hydroxide as precipitation agent. The concentration of reactants, morphology, particle size and degree of agglomeration was evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The aqueous nitrate solution of Y^{3+} was prepared by dissolving yttria powders (99.99 %,) in diluted nitric acid (HNO_3) and deionized water under stirring and heating, then diluted into 0.1 M with deionized water. The solution of Ce^{3+} was prepared by dissolving cerium nitrate (99.99 %,) in deionized water then diluted into 0.1M with deionized water. The mixed metal nitrate solution was dripped into a 0.5 M ammonium solution, under continuous rapid stirring, ensuring there was sufficiently high excess of ammonia to eliminate any pH fluctuations throughout the process. The mixed metal nitrate solution was added with the use of peristaltic pump at 5.0 ml/min, completing the reaction in 24 h. The mixed solution turned to opaque white slurry. After 12 h aging the slurry was vacuum filtered through filter paper and the resulting white precipitate washed with distilled water. The washed precipitate was dried overnight in air at $100^\circ C$. The dried precipitate was crushed and ground in an agate mortar and pestle, and calcined in air for 3 h at $700^\circ C$ (heating rate $10^\circ C/min$). Ultrasonication (20 kHz) was then used to de-agglomerate the nanopowder, using calculated amounts of Y_2O_3 powder and ammonium solution to adjust the pH value of the suspension, and using Commercial dispersants Dolapix CE 64 (Zaubax, Austria) or Darvan CN (Vanderbilt Minerals, Germany). Ultrasonication was applied in order to de-agglomerate the suspension. After sonication particle size, distribution and Zeta potential were determined as a function of pH and sonication time using particle size analyser (Brookhaven 90Plus BI-Zeta). Green compacts were prepared by pressure filtration of the ultrasonically de-agglomerated stabilized yttria suspension. The pressure filtration was performed in special die with the diameter of 15 mm. The suspension (20 wt. % solid loading) was poured into the die and after closing the mould, pressure 20 bar was applied through a hydraulic press. The water from the suspension was drained through massive perforated metal bottom with polymeric membrane (pore size $0.2\ \mu m$).

CHARACTERIZATION OF POWDERS

Crystallization temperatures of the pre-calcined powders were determined by differential scanning calorimetry combined with thermogravimetry (Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter TG / DTA / DSC). Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were acquired using powder X-ray diffractometer (Panalytical Empyrean DY1098). The Scherrer equation was used to the size of coherently diffracting domains, which in ideal case can be identified as the primary size of individual particles. The Scherrer equation can be written as:

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$$

Particle size distributions and particle morphologies were determined through scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-7600 F / EDS / WDS / EBSD)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal behaviour of yttria precipitate

Figure 1 presents results of DTA and related TG analysis of prepared $[Y_2(NO_3)_3 \cdot xY(OH)_3 \cdot yH_2O]$ precipitate. First broad endothermic peak up to 200 °C is related to dehydration of free and physically absorbed molecular water. Similarly as it is in [12, 13] dehydration of chemisorbed and combined water from $Y(OH)_3$ and α - $Y(OH)_3$ represents the endothermic peak at 350°C. The dehydration of structural water from YOOH phase occurs at around 450°C which confirms DTA data – at this temperature weak endothermic peak can be found [13, 14]. Because of HNO_3 presence during dissolving of yttria the basic yttrium hydroxy-nitrate complex $[Y_2(NO_3)_3 \cdot xY(OH)_3 \cdot yH_2O]$ is formed. Decomposition of such a complexes takes place about 530 °C and this temperature is also related to the beginning of the yttrium oxide crystallization [12,15]. Consequently, according to TG/ DTA decomposition of prepared yttria precursor is completed at 600 °C and with further increasing of the temperature no exo- nor endothermic effect can be detected.

Fig.1. DTA/TGA data for the precipitated hydroxide precursor

XRD analysis: determination of phase composition.

Figure 2. shows the XRD patterns of Y_2O_3 powder calcined at 700°C. As shown in the figure, the pure cubic Y_2O_3 phase was obtained with good crystallinity and the primary particle size of approximately 50nm, as determined from the Scherer equation.

Microstructure analysis

Figure 3. shows the SEM micrograph of synthesised Y_2O_3 powder. The powder is agglomerated with the primary particle size of approximately 55 nm, which is in good accord with the X-ray diffraction data.

Fig 2. XRD pattern of prepared Y_2O_3 powder calcined at 700 °C

Fig 3. SEM micrograph of the prepared Y_2O_3 powder

Particle size distribution

Figure 4. summarizes the changes in particle size of yttria powder with the sonication time. Extension of the ultrasonication time results in significant reduction of both the mean size of powder particles, and the width of the particle size distribution, indicating de-agglomeration of the yttria powder. The error bar on graph represents the particle size distribution at different time interval. As can be seen particle size distribution narrows with the increasing of the sonication time. The best results were achieved after 32 minutes sonication time. However, the mean size of 200 nm clearly shows that the powder was not de-agglomerated down to primary particle size, and hard agglomerates with the diameter of about 200 nm are still present.

Fig 4. The change of particle size of the Y_2O_3 powder with the sonication time

Fig.5. The results of Zeta potential measurements of yttria suspensions with different dispersants

Zeta potential and stability of suspension

The zeta potential of Y_2O_3 as function of pH is indicated in Fig. 5. Two different dispersants were used with the concentration of 2.0 wt. %: (Dolapix CE 64 and Darvan CN). According to literature the stability of the particles occurs zeta potential more than -30 mV [16]. The ammonia-water based Y_2O_3 suspension without dispersant shows zeta potential indicative values up to almost -30 mV. Yet, when the dispersant was used zeta-potential of the suspension reaches a maximum of ~35 mV. Both of the dispersant show similar values of zeta-potential in tested pH area; however, sedimentation rate of yttria suspension using Dolapix CE64 is lower when compared to Darvan CN [17], therefore Dolapix CE64 was selected for further experiments. Green compacts prepared by vacuum-pressure filtration out of yttria suspension stabilized with Dolapix CE64 reach relative density 43 %.

CONCLUSION

$Y_{1.99}Ce_{0.01}O_3$ nanopowder was synthesized via precipitation method. Partly agglomerated powders with the primary size of nanoparticles 55 nm and with cubic crystal structure were prepared. Ultra-sonication of yttria suspension de-agglomerated the particles to the mean size of 200 nm. Stabilization of the yttria suspension was reached in ammonia based water suspension with the addition of Dolapix CE64 as a dispersant. The green compact prepared by vacuum-pressure filtration method has the relative density about 43 %.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of VEGA 2/0026/17, SAS-MOST 2015-06 and FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.L. Coble. Transparent Alumina , US Patent 3,026,210. Mar. 20; (1962)
- [2] R.L. Coble, J. Appl. Phys. 32 (1961) 787.
- [3] G.C. Wei, J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. 38 (2005) 3057.
- [4] P.J. Patel, G.A. Gilde, P.G. Dehmer, J.W. McCauley, Proc. Soc. Photo-Opt. Instrum. Eng. 4102 (2000) 1.
- [5] V. Lupei, A. Lupei, A. Ikesue, Opt. Mater. 30 (2008) 1781.
- [6] J. Li, Y. Pan, Y. Zeng, W. Liu, B. Jiang, J. Guo, Journal Refract. Metals Hard Mater. 39 (2013) 44.
- [7] C. Greskovich, S. Duclos, Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci. 27 (1997) 69.
- [8] A. Ikesue, T. Kinoshita, K. Kamata Journal American Ceramic Society, 78, 1033-1040 (1995).
- [9] G.D. Miles, R.A.J. Sambell, J. Rutherford, G.W. Stephens, Journal British Ceramic Society, 66, 319 (1967)
- [10] R.W. Rice, Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 54, 205–207 (1971)
- [11] C. Greskovich, M.J. Curran, C.R. Oclair. Journal American Ceramic Society , 55, 324–325 (1972)
- [12] H. Gong, T. Ding-Yuan, H. Hui, Z. Tian-Shu, M. Journal of Effect Mater. Chem. Phys, 112, 423426, (2008)
- [13] M. Aghazadeh, A. Nozad, H. Adelhani, and M. Ghaemi, Journal of the Electrochemical Society, vol. 157, no. 10, pp. D519–D522, (2010).
- [14] R. Srinivasan, N. R. Yogamalar, J. Elanchezhian, R. J. Joseyphus, and A. C. Bose, Journal of Alloys and Compounds, vol. 496, no. 1-2, pp. 472–477, (2010).
- [15] L. Muresan, E. J. Popovici, R. Grecu, and L. B. Tudoran, . Journal of Alloys and Compounds, vol. 471, no. 1-2, pp. 421–427, (2009)
- [16] D.C. Grahame, *Chemical Review*, 41, 441-451 (1987).
- [17] Lingling Jin, Xiaojian Mao, Shiwei . Ceramics International 35 (2009) 925–927.